

SPACE TOURISM.

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Abstract: Space tourism is privately funded spaceflight into Earth's orbit for recreational or scientific research purposes. The idea of space tourism was first introduced in the series of works by Barron Hilton and Eric Kraft published in 1967. At first, they tried to promote the idea of space commercialization. At that time it was unsuccessful. This article provides information on space tourism and its development.

Key words: Space tourism, space, Mars planet, travel, International Space Station, astronaut.

Space tourism began to develop actively at the end of the 20th century. In 1986, at the International Astronautical Congress (English: International Astronautical Congress), a lecture was presented on the topic "Potential economic consequences of the development of space tourism", which caused a great discussion not only in scientific, but also in business circles.

The first tourist was to be the American teacher Christy McAuliffe. He died during the launch of the space shuttle Challenger in 1986. After this incident, the US government passed a law prohibiting non-professionals from flying into space. In 1990 and 1991, the first commercial cosmonauts - Toyohiro Akiyama (Japan) and Helen Sharman (Great Britain) launched Soyuz TM-11 / Soyuz TM-10 and Soyuz TM-12 as part of privately funded projects of TBS and Juno television companies. / flew to the orbital station "Mir" on the Soyuz TM-11 spacecraft. (Consortium of British Companies).

Space tourism is a step already taken. In 2001, an American businessman named Dennis Tito traveled to space for a week. The first thoughts about space flights and space travel appeared first in works of fiction. In particular, Jules Verne's book "From the Earth to the Moon" was published in 1865. Another fantasy writer Edward Hale's "Brick Moon" also tells about the adventures of people who accidentally fly into space and are on a space trip. Of course, sometimes non-scientific textures are used in works of art, but they are very important in increasing people's interest in science, especially astronomy and technology. It can be said that the theme of space travel is also sufficiently covered in the art of cinema. For example, Ridley Scott's movie "The Martian" (2015) was watched by many. The movie "Passengers" directed by Morten Tildum and released in 2016 is also considered one of the good works on this topic (in any case, it won an Oscar!). The film that covered the topic of space travel for the first time with great success was, without a doubt, the film "2001: A Space Odyssey".

Directed by Stanley Kubric Today, the issue of space travel has already moved from the pages of fiction to reality, and now there are even tour operators engaged in the organization of space tourism. For example, the company "Space Adventures" provides services in this field. After Dennis Tito, the first space traveler mentioned above, 6 more people have traveled to space and returned (one of them - US billionaire Charles Simoni even went into space twice). Naturally, a space tourism ticket is not cheap and only billionaires can afford it. For example, in 2001, Dennis Tito paid \$20 million for a flight to the ISS (International Space Station).k and now a classic of the genre, this film hit the big screens in 1968 and won four Oscars in 1969 (definitely recommend watching).But being a billionaire is not enough to go on a space trip. One must also be physically

fit and fit enough to withstand the rigors of flight. Therefore, buying space travel with money is only one side of the issue.

The next closest space trip to us is planned for October 2021, and Elon Musk's Crew Dragon spacecraft will take tourists to the SpaceX section of the ISS at a cost of \$55 million per person and return. Also, a new tour operator, Axiom, is entering the field of space tourism, and it is he who is organizing the trip in October. For \$55 million, space tourists spend 8 days on the ISS. Also, NASA itself wants to start work on space tourism, but the price they offer per person is 58 million. As you can see, there is now competition between tour operators in space travel. Now tourists are offered not only a flight to the ISS, but even a flight to the Moon. Accordingly, it can be said that the ticket for space travel will probably become "cheaper" from now on. In any case, analysts predict that by 2030 the space tourism market will reach \$3 billion. In order to reduce the number of zeros in the ticket price from 6 to 5, there are also plans to make the space flight cheaper by making it in a suborbital direction, on special planes.

From July 20, 2021, the richest man on the planet, Jeff Bezos, was in space... Mars has always attracted humanity. In the future, when the Red Planet is colonized by humans, it will be possible to conduct tours on the planet. Mars is a great tourist destination. Huge volcanoes, deep canyons and craters can be found here. In the future, the Red Planet will be an interesting tourist destination when the first human colonies appear on the planet. The publication "Focus" collected several places that can become a popular tourist center. Mount Olympus is the highest volcano in the Solar System. According to NASA, it is located in the volcanic region of Tharsis. Olympus is almost three times higher than Everest (8.9 km). Olympus rises to a height of 25 km. It's not just a mountain - it's a huge shield volcano formed from lava slowly flowing down its slopes. This means that future tourists will climb the mountain without much difficulty, since the average slope is only 5%. At the top of the mountain, there is an impressive depression about 85 km wide, formed by magma chambers and falling down.

Of course, the question of space travel is, at the moment, an extraordinarily expensive pastime that only a few people on our planet can afford. However, in the coming years, many people will have the opportunity to fly into space, feel like Gagarin or Neil Armstrong, and walk around the moon for free (!). Yes, you read that right, it is possible to travel to the moon for free. The fact is that in 2018, Japanese art tycoon Yusaku Maezawa, who became the first customer for a space flight to the Moon in Elon Musk's Starship spacecraft, also went to look for a companion to "circulate the Moon" with him. The project is called "DearMoon", according to which Maezawa has single-handedly booked all the space on the Starship spaceship and is now selecting talented people to fly to the moon together. According to his idea, several art-loving companions should be inspired to create new works of art by flying with him to the moon.

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